

Translations and the Gender Gap in the German National Library: A Case Study for Women Writers

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Context

The underrepresentation of women writers on the translation publishing market is apparent in bestseller lists, prize lists, but also translation databases. In a 2018 report on the translation publishing market in “Western” Europe, Wischenbart et al. (2016) noted that both the pool of bestselling and midlist authors is not balanced in terms of gender and that “in not a single year did female authors outnumber their male colleagues. (Wischenbart et al. 2019, 27)¹ The authors argue that “Western European bestseller markets are a regionally enclosed, globalized and male-dominated area.” (ibid.) The gender gap appears to be a global issue with the PEN Translation Prize, the ratio being 7:1 in favor of men over its fifty-year history (see Carson and Price 2019), and “less than one-third of translations published in the UK are by women authors” (Sanders 2022). Research on the 3% Translation Database of books published in the U.S. resounds these results and reports a decrease of the gender gap of 26% of authors identifying as female before 2014 and a 47% for 2022-2024. (Post 2023) To date, these tendencies still persist in recommended reading lists on platforms such as Wikipedia, which only lists twenty “classics” by female writers. Of the Deutsche Welle 100 must-read German works in translation only 1/3rd are by women writers. (Derbyshire 2018) The Index Translationum, one of the most prestigious databases for translations, only has eight women writers in the top 50 most translated authors.

It so therefore not surprising that this tendency is also present in some of the prestigious book prizes. Only seventeen women writers have won the Nobel Prize in Literature (14.28% of 119 awarded), three of whom are Germanophone writers: Nelly Sachs (1966), Elfriede Jelinek (2004), and Herta Müller (2009).² In 2009, Herta Müller only had one book translated into English, “more than her fellow female Nobel laureates Gabriela Mistral, Grazia Deledda, and Nelly Sachs, none of whom had any until after their award”. (Cain 2017) After having received the Nobel prize, Herta Müller’s novel *Atemschaukel* (2009) appeared as 24 trans-

lations in the year 2010 alone. Müller’s case not only shows how an international prize can augment the number of translated titles significantly, but also to what extent the translations of these women writers have not been prioritized prior to winning the Nobel Prize.

The selection of writers for book lists, literary prizes, and translations are all symptoms of a larger issue, that of the invisibility of women writers in translation in both academia and the publishing market. Scholars such as Bergenmar and Leppänen have noted the underrepresentation of women writers in world literature book list but also the absence of gender in world literary as well as large-scale literary studies. In other words, not only is there a lack of women writers but also of studies on the gender gap. They argue that the underlying reason for that lack is the continuous focus on the canon in which women have been left out and ignored as a result of power relations.³ In her book *FRAUEN LITERATUR: Abgewertet, vergessen, wiederentdeckt* (2021), Nicole Seifert makes a similar argument to Bergenmar and Leppänen, saying that canonization is a structural problem, according to which the literature of female authors has always been marginalized and not evaluated, reviewed, and commented on in the same way as male authors. It is therefore becoming increasingly important to make these canonization mechanisms, as well as the institutions that are structurally involved in them, visible.

For Belle and Guénette notions related to the representation of women writers in translation come down to a question of visibility and argue that “a common theme in the recent historiography of both women and translation has been the question of visibility.” (Belle and Guénette 2024, 36) This applies not only to the old issue of translator invisibility (see Venuti 2008), but also author visibility. As a response to the invisibility of women writers recent actions have made it their mission to make women writers in translation more visible. The blog “Women in Translation” month is one of many initiatives to increase visibility of women writers and translators by featuring new translations, translators’ commentary, and critical pieces on the canonization of literature. “Diekanon” is an initiative that compiles lists of underrepresented authors, therefore creating an anti-canon of women writers. “Frauenzählen” is another initiative from Germany to visualize the gender gap from statistics on gender ratios in literary prizes as well as reviews. Additionally, large-scale bibliographic projects that aim at making women writers more visible such as Orlando, the Bibliography of English Women Writers (1500-1640), Canada’s Early Women Writers, American Women Writers: Bibliography 1820-1829, the CCC subset: Women in translation and print 1641-1660 (Belle and Guénette 2025) and many more. All these initiatives push towards visibility and aim at not only representing but also promoting women writers in response to the systemic, institutional invisibility of women writers.

Research questions

These tendencies are promising; however, the question remains to what extent this is also the case for the German literature canon as it is conserved in and accessible through the German National library (DNB). Can we observe the same tendency and gender gap in national libraries such as the DNB, which are repositories of memory and canonization? And how can we make visible women writers in these repositories without reproducing the same gender imbalances that we critique? In the next two sections, I present a method to make visible the gender gap by using the information on author gender in the DNB's authority files. I then present preliminary results on the most translated women writers in the DNB as well as a categorisation based on the factors that drive their translationalism (number of translated titles, linguistic distribution, geographic reach).

In line with Bergenmar and Leppänen, Belle and Guénette, and Seifert, I argue that national collections are a central space in which power relations are visible and can be investigated by looking at collection and cataloguing practices in regard to gender. In accordance with the mission of existing bibliographic projects to amplify the visibility of women writers in our cultural repositories, this project aims to illustrate how digital tools can be a means to visualize translations by women writers and languages other than English in national collections.

Dataset and Methodology

As a source, the "Mapping German fiction in translation" dataset (Teichmann 2025), which includes close to 36.000 titles published between 1980 and 2020 by 6047 authors into 86 languages extracted from the German National library (DNB), has been used. By using an SRU query in Python, for each author, the GND authority files have been extracted. From the list of authors, I only kept the ones that have "female" (weiblich) in MARC21 field 375 (subfield \$a) in the authority file from the GND. This left me with 1742 authors and 7103 titles after filtering the table of titles in the "Mapping German fiction in translation" dataset.⁴

My analysis of the dataset consists of two parts: visualizing the gender gap in the DNB and secondly identifying and discussing the most translated women writers of German literature according in the national library. In line with previous studies on the gender gap in reports and in articles, I first calculated the percentage of titles by authors that are identified as female in the GND overall and per year. Secondly, I highlighted the top translated female authors and identified the factors of each author that drive their translationalism. To identify the most translated authors I calculated the sums of titles, translated languages, and publishing places per author and ranked them in descending order. As a second step I further grouped the top 10 most translated women writers in the DNB into four categories according to their most translated original work, linguistic distri-

bution, and geographic reach. The statistical findings are contextualized with details about the author's literary prizes and preferred genres.

Secondly, I identified the most translated women writers by looking at the number of languages (translationalism) and the total number of translated titles (canonicity) per author. Combining these two measures allows us to place authors in the canonical field (authors with many titles, re-translations, and re-publications into the same languages) or the translational field (authors that have translations into many languages and therefore are linguistically distributed). To identify the top translated authors hence, I calculated the number of languages the author has been translated into and the sum of their translated titles. Additionally, I also measured the geographic reach of an author's translation by calculating the sum of their publishing places (where their translations were published). Ranking the authors in descending order according to their title sums allows us to look at the top 20 most translated women writers. I also calculated the percentages of authors for each measure with the mean to describe the overall tendencies in terms of translations in the DNB.

Findings

For titles and authors, we can observe a wide gender gap in my dataset overall. My results correlate with the findings for the UK translation market, representing less than a third of translated titles and authors are identified as women in the DNB. Only 1742 are female according to the GND, which represents 22.4% of all 6047 authors in the "Mapping German fiction in translation dataset". The vast majority (77.6%) are male identified. Translated titles by female authors represent 20.5% of all titles in the dataset, meaning that 4/5 of all titles are by male authors.

The author with the most translations (Hedwig Courths-Mahler) has 372 titles with an average of 5.8 titles per author. However, the top 20 authors have 35% of all titles and 79% of women authors have less than 5 titles, meaning that only 20% of authors surpass that threshold, while the majority are not frequently translated.⁵ Additionally, only a few authors are translated into many languages, with a maximum of 38 languages (Elfriede Jelinek).

Aim

Collecting and presenting preliminary findings on women writers' translationalism and the gender gap in translation in the DNB highlight imbalances but also provide a basis on which we can make visible the women writers in the canon and their roles in the global circulation of German literature. I hope to thereby illustrate that we can use digital tools to make visible the gender gap and women writers in national collections.

This study aims to illustrate that combining digital humanities tools, drawing on national collections for data on

canonization, and exploring methods for identifying the driving factors behind women writers' translational trajectories allows us to "re-read literary history from a gendered perspective" (Bergenmar and Leppänen 2017, 237). While data analysis can give us interesting starting points, deeper research on these writers is often required. Institutional data can only tell us so much and qualitative and biographical work still needs to be done. By doing so, I wish to show what "digital humanities have to offer that can promote specialized, localized, and gendered knowledge. (Bergenmar and Leppänen 2017, 233)

Not only does my study compile the first dataset on women writers of German fiction in translation extracted from the DNB, but it also proposes explorative methods to categorize authors according to what drives their translationism. I hope to show that using quantitative methods and data from library collections can bring gender research into the digital humanities, with research on translations as a point of departure for this endeavor.

Footnotes

1. "In 2016, the gender distribution was almost equal, but in all other years, the number of female authors was below eight. This ratio worsened from 2012–2017 in comparison to 2006–2011." (Wischenbart et al. 2019, 27)
2. Recent developments however show an approximation to 50/50 (whether this is the goal or not is debatable), e.g. of New York Times bestseller lists which had 48% women in 2016. (Cima 2022)
3. They argue that "which works are translated at different times reflects relations of power, including gender" (Bergenmar and Leppänen 2017, 243).
4. The dataset and code are published in a public GitHub repository: <https://github.com/lisateichmann/Mapping-German-Women-Writers-Translations>
5. 64% of women authors have only one translated title.

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